

EFFECT OF MORINGA (*Moringa oleifera*) AQUEOUS LEAF AND ROOT EXTRACTS IN THE PERFORMANCE OF AFRICAN CATFISH (*Clarias gariepinus*) FINGERLINGS

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ABSTRACT

Plant extracts with phytobiotic properties have been added to feeds to improve feed utilization and overall growth of animals including fish species. This study investigated the impact of the aqueous leaf and root extracts of the Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) on the overall performance of African Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) fingerlings, by the addition of aqueous extracts to the culture water. The experiment had 4 treatments with 3 replicates; T₀, T₁, T₂, and T₃ represented the control (extract-free), treatment with aqueous leaf extract, treatment with aqueous root extract, and treatment with both aqueous leaf and root extracts in equal proportions, respectively. The results revealed considerable variations in the overall performance of fish across the treatments. T₂ had the best (16.43g) Feed intake (FI), followed by T₀ (14.64g) and T₃ (13.76g) which had similar results, with no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) with T₁ (11.45g) having the least value. Similarly, T₂ had the highest total weight gain (TWG) (55.84g), followed by T₀ (49.60g) and T₃ (47.44g), which had similar results, with no significant difference ($p < 0.05$). This study concludes that aqueous root extracts of Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) added to the culture medium of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) fingerlings, can enhance feed intake and growth performance.

Keywords: aqueous, plant extracts, phytobiotic, *Clarias gariepinus*

INTRODUCTION

The African catfish is the choicest option for fish farmers in Nigeria for many reasons, including high tolerance towards adverse environmental conditions, disease resistance, and high Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) (Olagunju *et al.*, 2022). The growth of aquaculture in Nigeria is now largely boosted by a steady rise in catfish culture. African catfish is popular in the market and has great potential to increase

the rapidly growing Nigerian aquaculture (Adewumi and Olaleye, 2011). Moringa has been studied severally for its potential benefits in the culture of *Clarias gariepinus*, including nutritional value, growth promotion, and immune system enhancement (Hussain *et al.*, 2020). Parts of moringa and their extracts are known to have phytobiotic properties and contain certain minerals (Anjorin, 2010) capable of boosting the overall performance of

African catfish in culture. Martin *et al.* (2016) reported that the leaves of the plant can contribute to the growth and overall health of *Clarias gariepinus*. Eunice *et al.* (2018), included other parts of *Moringa oleifera* to obtain various bioactive compounds, including phenolics, alkaloids, and flavonoids, which exhibit antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties, to bolster the immune response of *Clarias gariepinus*. Utilization of Moringa for these purposes has been carried out mostly, by addition as inclusions in the diet, and the use of root extracts of the plant has hardly been reported. Thus, this study investigated the impact of using Moringa aqueous leaf and root extracts in the culture of African catfish fingerlings, by adding extracts directly to the culture medium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Materials

At three weeks old, 120 *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings were procured from the hatchery unit of a reputable fish farm in Benin City Edo State. The very healthy,

same nutritional history and the same size fish seed were acclimatized for one week before the commencement of the experiment. A total of 12 culturing tanks (0.464m x 0.323m 0.24m) each with a water carrying capacity of about twenty litres (20L), were used for this study.

The Moringa parts (Roots [Plate 1] and leaves [Plate 2]) obtained locally, were thoroughly washed, and disinfected by complete immersion in salt water for 3 -5 minutes. Afterwards, the plant parts were rinsed with salt-free room temperature water, chopped into small bits (roots), and air dried, after which they were blended using an industrial blender before extraction. Infusion techniques were applied to extract the bioactive substances present. 60g of the ground particles were soaked in one litre (1L) of water for 24 hours (Alabi *et al.*, 2017; Portugaliza and Fernandez, 2011). The preparation was then filtered using a strainer to separate the debris and filtrate. The concentrated extract was then placed in a sealed, clean container and refrigerated until needed.

Plate 1: Ground Moringa roots

Plate 2: Ground Moringa leaves

Dilution Ratio of Aqueous Extracts

The dilution ratio for all aqueous extracts during application was 100ml of Moringa aqueous extract per 1000ml of water (Portugaliza and Fernandez, 2012; Alabi *et al.*, 2017). It should be noted that in the case of T₃ (containing both root and leaf extracts), aqueous leaf and root extracts were added in equal proportions, contributing 50ml each before dilution.

Fish Management

A total of one hundred and twenty (120) *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings were cultured using twelve (12) plastic tanks, each accommodating ten (10) fish to which various treatments of aqueous root, leaf, and combination of both extracts of *Moringa oleifera* were applied except for the control which had no extracts for five weeks. Within this time frame, there was routine maintenance of the fish culture facility to ensure that ideal water quality

was maintained. Fish were fed to satiation daily between 8:00hrs-9:00hrs and 16:00hrs-17:00hrs. Extract(s) application/reapplication was carried out twice a week; once every three days after changing the water in the culture medium. This procedure was consistent throughout the five-week duration of the study.

Data collection

Fish samples collected randomly from each treatment were weighed initially and subsequently weekly using Durascale D2, 300 x 0.01g capacity pocket scale. The feed was also weighed using the scale. The growth and nutrient utilization were determined in terms of feed intake (FI), total weight gain (TWG), average daily weight gain (ADG), percentage relative weight gain (%RWG), specific growth rate (SGR), feed conversion ratio (FCR), and survival rate (SR) as follows:

$$\text{Feed Intake (I) (g/day)} = \frac{\text{Total Feed consumed}}{\text{Number of days}}$$

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$$\text{Total Weight Gain (TWG) (g)} = \text{Final Weigh} - \text{Initial Weight}$$

$$\text{Average Daily Weight Gain (ADG) (g/day)} = \frac{\text{h} - \text{h}}{\text{h}}$$

$$\text{Relative Weight Gain (RWG) (\%)} = \frac{\text{Final Weight} - \text{Initial Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Specific Growth Rate (\%/day)} = \frac{\text{Ln}(\text{Final weight}) - \text{Ln}(\text{Initial weight})}{\text{Days}}$$

$$\text{Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)} = \frac{\text{Total Feed Intake (g)}}{\text{Total Weight Gain (g)}}$$

$$\text{Survival Rate (SR)} = \frac{\text{Number of Survivors}}{\text{Initial Number}} \times 100$$

Water quality parameters

Water quality parameters measured were dissolved oxygen which was measured *in situ* with WTM, Oxical-SL portable electronic probe, Temperature was monitored using mercury in glass thermometer, and the water pH measured using AA wipes 8-in-1 Aquarium Test Kit for Fish Tanks by dipping the test strip number 7 into water for 2 seconds Remove the strip without shaking off excess water, then hold horizontally for 30 seconds and compare the colours to the chart for up to 99% accuracy and take necessary action.

Data analysis

The data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the Genstat statistical package Version 2009. Differences between mean were compared using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at $p=0.05$. Descriptive statistics were used to present results where relevant.

RESULTS

Water Quality Parameters

Table 1 shows that physico-chemical properties of the culture medium were within the recommended range for *Clarias gariepinus*, (Boyd, 1979).

Table 1: Water Quality Parameters

	TREATMENTS			
	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	6.06 ^a	4.86 ^c	5.77 ^b	5.23 ^b
Temperature (°C)	27.37 ^b	30.40 ^a	29.67 ^a	30.07 ^a
pH	5.68 ^b	6.87 ^a	6.65 ^a	6.63 ^a

Mean values across rows with the same superscript are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$)

Feed Intake (FI), Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR), and Survival Rate (SR) of Fish Across Various Treatments

Table 2 shows that T₂ had the best profile, having results significantly higher than all other treatments ($p > 0.05$). T₀ and T₃ followed (having similar results); not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). T₁ had the poorest values.

Feed Intake (FI)

T₂ (treatment with aqueous root extract) performed best (16.43g), followed by T₀ (control) and T₃ (treatments with both aqueous leaf and root extracts) which both had similar results, with no significant

difference ($p < 0.05$); (14.64g and 13.76g respectively). T₁ (treatment with aqueous leaf extract) had the lowest feed intake (11.45g).

Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)

Table 2 indicates that T₀, T₁, T₂, and T₃ were similar with no significant difference; $p < 0.05$ (0.2933, 0.3300, 0.2933, and 0.2900) respectively.

Survival Rate (SR)

Table 2 shows that the survival rates of fish across various treatments were similar; with no significant differences ($p < 0.05$) ranging from 86.67% - 96.67%.

Table 2: Feed Intake, Growth Performance, and Survival Rate of Fish

	TREATMENT				S.E.D
	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	
T. Weight Gain (g)	49.60 ^b	34.40 ^c	55.84 ^a	47.44 ^b	2.441
Feed Intake (g)	14.64 ^b	11.45 ^c	16.43 ^a	13.76 ^b	0.404
Avg. Daily Weight Gain (g/days)	1.420 ^b	0.983 ^c	1.597 ^a	1.357 ^b	0.0715
Relative Weight Gain (%)	653.5 ^b	486.8 ^c	784.6 ^a	622.2 ^b	45.3
FCR	0.2933 ^b	0.3300 ^a	0.2933 ^b	0.2900 ^b	0.01381
Specific Growth Rate (%/day)	5.833 ^{ab}	5.050 ^c	6.223 ^a	5.630 ^b	0.1856
Survival (%)	96.67 ^a	86.67 ^a	86.67 ^a	93.33 ^a	6.67

Mean values across rows with the same superscript are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$)

S.E.D: Standard Error of Differences of Mean

FCR: Feed Conversion Ratio

Growth Performance of Fish across Various Treatments

Total Weight Gain (TWG)

Table 2 shows that T₂ had the highest value (55.84g), followed by T₀ and T₃ which had similar results, with no significant difference ($p < 0.05$); (49.60g and 47.44g), and T₁ having the lowest value (34.40g).

Average Daily Weight Gain (ADWG)

T₂ had the highest value (1.597g) of average daily weight gain, followed by T₀ (1.420g) and T₃ (1.357g), which had similar results, with no significant differences ($p < 0.05$); and T₁ had the least value (0.983g).

Specific Growth Rate (SGR)

Table 2 indicates that T₀ and T₂, performed typically the same; with no significant difference ($p < 0.05$; 5.830%/day, and 6.223%/day respectively). T₃ wasn't significantly different from T₀ ($p < 0.05$; 5.630%/day and 5.83%/day respectively). T₂, on the other hand, performed the least with an SGR of 5.050%/day.

Relative Weight Gain (RWG)

Table 2 shows that T₂ had the highest RWG (784.6%), followed by T₀ and T₃, having similar results, with no significant differences; $p < 0.05$ (653.5% and 622.2%), and T₁ having the lowest RWG (486.8%).

DISCUSSION

Water Quality Parameters

The physico-chemical parameters (temperature, DO, and pH) during this study were within the recommended / tolerable range for *Clarias gariepinus*. This agrees with studies by Esien *et al.* (2018), and Ekelemu *et al.* (2022), where it was concluded that Moringa extracts improved culture water quality in their

feed trials. However, T₁ performed somewhat poorly with an average DO value of 4.86mg/l. This low value of dissolved oxygen was associated with the early set-in of pollution for this treatment (24hours - 36hours), characterized by a foul smell, an oil-like film forming on the surface of the culture water (usually breaking apart upon touch, but resurfacing after a while), as well as permanent air bubbles forming on the surface of the culture water. The appearance of such substances on the water surface for the other treatments occurred hours later, 48 to 54 hours in T₃, and 66 to 72 hours in T₂. Changing the culture water simultaneously allows sufficient time for the absorption of the bioactive components of extracts; to elicit the much-anticipated growth response in study fish as recommended by Evans *et al.* (2005), and Chris *et al.*, (2016).

Feed Intake (FI) and Survival Rate (SR) of Fish Across Various Treatments

Feed Intake (FI)

T₂ had the best FI followed by T₀ and T₃ which were similar, with no significant difference; $p < 0.05$. T₂ had the best FI because it experienced the highest delay in observable water quality changes setting in between 66 to 72 hours after administering the treatment, compared to other treatments where water quality changes in terms of colouration as opposed to treatment T₁. This fostered the absorption of the bioactive components of the root extract by study fish, thus, enhancing fish appetite and resulting in enhanced feed intake. Suffice it to mention that the impact of the aqueous root extract on the colour of the culture medium in T₂ was mild and not as severe as in T₁, therefore, not impacting light intensity, and not affecting feed negatively. An

important point is to be certain that light affects fish growth through better food conversion efficiency and not just through stimulated [food intake](#). Most fish rely on vision to feed, in the first place and light intensity affects the feeding behaviour of various fish species, such as Pacific codfish (*Gadus macrocephalus*) and Mandarin fish (*Siniperca kneri*) ([Li et al., 2013](#)). In this case, the perceived excess of extract constituents, shown in the colouration, may have been the major reason for the observed disruption in feed intake as the study fish is nocturnal.

Survival Rate (SR)

In the area of survival rate, the outcomes for all treatments were similar, with no significant difference ($p < 0.05$). Essentially, even though the DO condition in T_1 was considerably lower than that for other treatments due to extended pollution, it had no serious implications on survival as the water was changed in time for all Treatments.

Growth Performance; Total Weight Gain (TWG), Average Daily Weight Gain (ADWG), and Relative Weight Gain (RWG) of fish across various Treatments

Treatment with Moringa Aqueous Root Extract (T_2)

T_2 had the best growth performance profile, with TWG (55.84g), ADWG (1.597g/days), and RWG (784.6%). This performance index is so because treatment T_2 had the best conditions; it experienced the least pollution, and the water was always having no turbidity issues observed as in the case of other treatments especially T_1 , experimental fish were also exposed to possibly a more favourable

influence from the constituents of the root extract, thus, eliciting the observed growth response in study fish.

Treatment T_1 (Moringa Aqueous Leaf Extract)

T_1 had the lowest performance with TWG (34.40g), ADWG (0.983g/days), and RWG (486.8%). The cause of this poor performance can be attributed to the high colouration imparted by the extract on the culture medium suggesting some sort of pollution during this study. The low D.O level in T_1 compared to the rest, coupled with the perceived excess of extract constituents, caused a measure of stress to the study fish, adversely affecting fish appetite, and by extension, feed intake, and ultimately reducing the overall growth performance of fish.

Treatment T_3 (Moringa Aqueous Leaf and Root Extracts)

T_3 was similar to T_0 , but better than T_1 . The significantly reduced growth performance in T_3 compared to T_2 which performed best was caused by the presence of aqueous leaf extract, which was responsible for the much earlier set in of pollution in T_3 , and reduced growth performance. The aqueous root extract component which was present in equal proportions with the aqueous leaf extract component meant a 50% reduction in aqueous leaf extract present in T_3 , thus, reduction in excess dissolved organic compounds associated with the leaf extract, implying better culture medium conditions as opposed to treatment group T_1 , which had 100% leaf extract. The root extract component of T_3 no doubt played a crucial role in enhancing the growth performance of culture fish. It is therefore apparent why T_3 had a growth performance profile that was better than that of T_1 .

Treatment T₀ (no Extracts; Control)

T₀ was similar to T₃ with no significant difference, significantly lower than T₂, and significantly higher than T₁. T₀ did not do quite as well as T₂, because, even though culture conditions were favourable, no additional organic compounds were added to the culture medium to further enhance growth as are recent practices and as recommended by Haruna and Zannah (2023). T₀ performed better than T₁ because there was no leaf extract present to undermine performance.

CONCLUSION

The outcome of this study scientifically proves that the aqueous root extract of

Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) in culture medium enhances the overall performance of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*). The use of aqueous leaf extract of Moringa, on the other hand, did not give the desired results at the concentration it was used in this study, while the use of a combination of both aqueous leaf and root extracts resulted in growth performance similar to when fish are cultured with no extracts of the Moringa plant. A further study is recommended at a lower concentration of the leaf extract of the study plant.

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